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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of a Water -Based Sunscreen Lotion Incorporating Glycine Max Extract

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ABSTRACT

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a water-based sunscreen lotion utilizing Glycine max (soybean) extract, a natural source of isoflavones, flavonoids, and antioxidants with known photoprotective properties. In light of growing concerns over the safety and environmental impact of synthetic UV filters, the use of herbal alternatives offers a promising solution. The extract was prepared through cold maceration, followed by its incorporation into lotion formulations at varying concentrations. The prepared formulations were assessed for organoleptic properties, pH, spreadability, homogeneity, extrudability, and Sun Protection Factor (SPF). Results demonstrated favorable physical stability, good aesthetic attributes, and SPF values increasing proportionally with the concentration of Glycine max extract. The highest SPF recorded was 21.66 for the formulation with 1.5% extract. These findings suggest that Glycine max extract serves as a viable, safe, and eco-friendly alternative for natural sunscreen formulations. Further studies including in vivo testing are warranted to substantiate these results.

INTRODUCTION

The human skin, the largest organ of the body serves as a barrier of defense. against external physical, chemical, and biological stressors. Among these, ultraviolet radiation from the sun poses significant threat, leading to various adverse effects such as erythema (sunburn), premature aging, hyperpigmentation, and the development of skin cancers. In tropical and subtropical regions,

where UV radiation exposure is more intense and prolonged, the need for effective sun protection becomes even more crucial.(1) Sunscreens have emerged as Among the most efficient means of protecting the skin from UV radiation. These formulations contain UV filters that either absorb, reflect, or scatter the harmful rays. Based on wavelength, UV radiation is divided into three ranges: UVC (100–290 nm), which is primarily

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blocked by the ozone layer; UVB (290–320 nm), which causes sunburn and damages DNA; and UVA (320–400 nm), which reaches deeper into the skin and causes photoaging. The perfect sunscreen is safe, stable, and aesthetically pleasing, providing broad-spectrum protection against UVA and UVB radiation.(2) The effectiveness of a sunscreen is usually measured by its Sun Protection Factor (SPF), which quantifies the product's ability to prevent UVB-induced erythema. Traditional sunscreens often use synthetic chemical UV filters such as avobenzone, oxybenzone and octinoxate. While effective, these compounds have raised concerns due to their potential to cause skin irritation, allergic reactions, endocrine disruption, and environmental damage.(2) As a result, Interest in natural alternatives has increased, particularly those derived from plant-based sources.(3) One such promising bioactive plant is Glycine max, commonly known as soybean. The current study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a water-based sunscreen lotion incorporating Glycine max extract, aiming to provide a safe, effective, and eco-friendly photoprotective solution.

1.1 Importance of Herbal Sunscreens(4)

In response to the concerns associated with synthetic sunscreens, herbal formulations are gaining widespread attention in both academic and commercial sectors. These products are formulated using natural extracts rich in phytoconstituents that offer UV protection alongside additional skin benefits such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-aging, and moisturizing effects.

Herbal sunscreens aim to(5):

- Minimize or eliminate synthetic chemical filters

- Provide broad-spectrum protection using plant compounds
- Improve safety and tolerability, especially for sensitive skin
- Align with the global shift towards green chemistry and eco-conscious skincare

Among the natural compounds explored for photoprotection, polyphenols, flavonoids, isoflavones, and other antioxidants have shown great potential. These compounds absorb UV rays and neutralize free radicals, thereby preventing cellular damage caused by oxidative stress.

1.2 Glycine max (Soybean):

Glycine max, a member of the Fabaceae family, is widely cultivated for its nutritional, medicinal, and cosmetic benefits. Beyond its role as a protein-rich food crop, soybean seeds and extracts are rich in biologically active compounds, making them suitable for topical applications in skincare products, particularly sunscreens(5).

Key Phytoconstituents in Glycine max(6):

1. Isoflavones – such as genistein and daidzein, which mimic estrogen and support skin health by promoting collagen synthesis and skin elasticity.
2. Saponins – known for their cleansing, emulsifying, and antioxidant properties.
3. Phytosterols – which help maintain skin hydration and improve barrier function.
4. Essential fatty acids – contribute to skin repair and lipid balance.
5. Polyphenols and flavonoids – act as potent antioxidants, offering photoprotection and anti-aging benefits.

These phytochemicals have shown the ability to absorb UV rays within the UVA and UVB spectrum, effectively making soybean extracts a natural UV filter. Studies have demonstrated that

topical application of soy-based formulations leads to improvements in skin tone, reduction of photo-damage, and protection against oxidative stress-induced by UV exposure.(7)

1.3 Advantages of Using Glycine max in Sunscreens(8)

Incorporating Glycine max into sunscreen formulations offers multiple advantages, making it a holistic skincare ingredient:

- **Broad-spectrum UV Protection:** Isoflavones and polyphenols in soy absorb UV radiation effectively.
- **Antioxidant Activity:** Neutralizes reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated during sun exposure.
- **Skin Rejuvenation:** Stimulates collagen and elastin production, reducing signs of aging.
- **Anti-inflammatory Properties:** Soothes irritated skin and reduces UV-induced erythema.
- **Moisturizing Effect:** Enhances skin hydration and softness.
- **Non-toxic and Safe:** Minimal risk of skin irritation or allergies.
- **Eco-friendly:** Biodegradable and does not contribute to marine pollution like some synthetic filters.

The antioxidant potential of Glycine max is especially important in sunscreen formulations, as UV-induced free radical formation is a key mechanism of photoaging and skin cancer. By inhibiting lipid peroxidation and DNA damage, soybean extract helps maintain skin integrity and youthfulness.

1.4 Water-Based Formulations: A Modern Delivery System(10)

Today's consumers demand sunscreens that are lightweight, non-greasy, quick-drying, and

suitable for all skin types. Water-based formulations fulfill these requirements and are especially beneficial in hot, humid environments where oily or sticky formulations are uncomfortable.

Water-based lotions are typically oil-in-water emulsions that offer:

- Better Spreadability
- Faster absorption
- Less pore-clogging
- Improved user compliance

The incorporation of Glycine max extract into a water-based lotion ensures that its phytochemicals remain stable and effective, while also making the product cosmetically elegant and easy to apply. Water-based systems also allow for the dispersion of hydrophilic and amphiphilic herbal constituents, enhancing their availability at the skin surface.

1.5 Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Glycine max in Sunscreen Formulations(11)

Advantages

Natural UV Absorption

1 Glycine max is rich in isoflavones and polyphenolic compounds such as genistein and daidzein, which absorb UV radiation naturally, particularly in the UVB and UVA range, reducing skin damage caused by sunlight exposure.

2 Antioxidant Properties

The antioxidant components in soy extract help neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by UV rays, preventing oxidative stress, premature aging, and inflammation.

3 Anti-inflammatory Action

The formulation is advantageous for sensitive or inflammatory skin disorders since soy isoflavones have anti-inflammatory qualities that calm the skin.

4 Skin Rejuvenation and Anti-Aging

Glycine max enhances collagen and elastin synthesis, which supports skin firmness and elasticity, reducing fine lines and signs of photoaging.

5 Moisturizing Effect

The presence of essential fatty acids and saponins provides a hydrating and emollient effect, making the lotion ideal for daily skincare.

6 Safe and Non-Toxic

Being plant-derived, Glycine max is generally considered safe, non-irritant, and well-tolerated by most skin types, with a low risk of allergic reactions.

7 Eco-Friendly

As a botanical ingredient, Glycine max is sustainable and environmentally friendly, posing no threat to marine ecosystems—unlike certain synthetic UV filters.

DISADVANTAGES

1 Lower SPF Compared to Synthetics

While Glycine max provides measurable SPF, it may not match the high SPF values of synthetic agents unless used in higher concentrations or combined with other UV filters.

2 Potential Allergenicity in Some Individuals

Although rare, soy-based ingredients can cause allergic reactions in sensitive individuals or those with soy allergies.

3 Batch Variability

The quality and phytochemical composition of Glycine max extract may vary depending on cultivation, harvesting, and extraction conditions, which can impact reproducibility.

1.6 Ideal Properties of Sunscreen Lotion

1. The sunscreen lotion should be smooth, uniform, and homogeneous in appearance and texture.
2. It should exhibit good Spreadability without requiring excessive force and should be easily applied over large areas of the skin.
3. The formulation should maintain physical and chemical stability, ensuring no separation of phases or degradation of active ingredients.
4. The formulation must be non-toxic, non-irritant, and compatible with other excipients used in the preparation.
5. The emulsion system used in the lotion should be easily spreadable and form a uniform film over the skin, ensuring consistent sun protection.
6. It must be water-resistant or sweat-resistant to ensure prolonged activity during outdoor activities.
7. The pH of the lotion should be within the dermatologically acceptable range (typically 4.5–6.5).

1.6 Plant Profile:

Glycine max (Soybean)

Synonyms: Soybean, Soya bean, Soja, Soy

Biological Source: Soybean consists of the dried ripe seeds of *Glycine max* (L.) Merrill, belonging

to the family Fabaceae. The extract is obtained from the seeds and is rich in isoflavones and other Phyto actives.

Family: Fabaceae (Leguminosae)

Geographical Source: *Glycine max* is native to East Asia (particularly China and Japan) but is now cultivated extensively in countries such as the United States, Brazil, Argentina, India, and China.

Chemical Constituents:

The seeds of *Glycine max* are a rich source of isoflavones, flavonoids, saponins, sterols, terpenoids, fatty acids, and phenolic compounds. Among these, flavonoids, especially isoflavones, are of particular interest due to their potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and UV-protective properties, making soybean extract highly valuable in cosmeceutical formulations like sunscreen lotions. The major isoflavones identified include genistein, daidzein, and glycitein, often present in glycoside forms such as genistin, daidzin, and glycitin. These compounds absorb UV radiation, scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by UV exposure, and help reduce UV-induced skin damage, making them effective natural photoprotectants.

Other important constituents are:

- Phytosterols: β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, campesterol – known for anti-inflammatory and skin-barrier-enhancing activity.(15)
- Tocopherols (Vitamin E): Primarily α -tocopherol – protects skin lipids from UV-induced oxidation.(16)
- Saponins: Soyasaponin I, soyasaponin β g – provide anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory benefits.(17)
- Phenolic acids: Caffeic acid, ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid – function as antioxidants.(18)
- Tannins, lectins, and protease inhibitors (like trypsin inhibitors).(19)
- Polysaccharides: Including hemicellulose, raffinose, stachyose, and galactomannans – beneficial for skin hydration and texture.(20)
- Essential fatty acids: Linoleic acid (omega-6) and α -linolenic acid (omega-3), which help restore skin lipids and prevent photoaging.(21)

Flavonoids and UV-Protective Activity:

Flavonoids act as natural sunscreens by absorbing UV radiation in the UVB (290–320 nm) and UVA (320–400 nm) ranges.(22) Their antioxidant capacity neutralizes UV-induced free radicals, thereby protecting skin cells from DNA damage, inflammation, and early aging.(23)

Flavonoids Present in *Glycine max*:(24)

Fig no 1 Genistein(25)

Glycitein

Fig no 2 Glycitein (26)

Daidzein

Fig no 3 Daidzein(27)

Taxonomical Classification of *Glycine max* (28)(Soybean)

Sub class	Rosidae
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae (Leguminosae)
Genus	<i>Glycine</i>
Species	<i>Glycine max</i> (L.) Merrill

Table No.1 Taxonomical Classification(13)

Kingdom	Plantae
Sub kingdom	Tracheobionta (Vascular plants)
Division	Magnoliophyta (Angiosperms)
Class	Magnoliopsida (Dicotyledons)

2. Literature Review

Sr No	Title of the Study	Author(s)	Year	Journal	Key Findings
1	Development and Evaluation of Herbal Sunscreen Formulation	Swathimol S, Keziya Mary Shaji, Arya Prasad, Deepa S Nair, Deepa Cherian	2022	Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Health Sciences	Formulated herbal sunscreen; highest SPF among selected oils; good pH and spreadability.
2	Formulation and Evaluation of Cost-Effective Herbal Sunscreen Gel from Aqueous Extracts of Different Fruits	Probin Kr Roy et al.	2022	International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Nanotechnology	Prepared fruit-based herbal sunscreen; SPF and stability evaluated; effective formulations identified.

	of Mizoram, India				
3	Enhancing Sun Protection: Formulating and Assessing Herbal Sunscreen Formulations	Zaid Khan et al.	2023	RGUHS Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences	Compared herbal and synthetic sunscreens; herbal variants showed superior SPF and skin feel.
4	Formulation and In Vitro Evaluation of Sun Protection Factor of Herbal Sunscreen Cream Containing Butea monosperma, Neolamarckia cadamba, and Punica granatum Extracts	Manisha Sutar, Sanjay R Chaudhari, Macchindra J Chavan	2019	Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics	SPF and antioxidant activity increased in creams with these herbal extracts.
5	Development of Herbal Sunscreen Formulations from the Leaves of Sri Lankan Medicinal Plants, Hibiscus furcatus Wild. and Olax zeylanica Linn	C. E. Liyanaarachchi ¹ , M. Napagoda ¹ , S. Malkanthi ¹ , K. Abayawardana ¹ , S. Witharana ² , L. Jayasinghe	2022	Journal of Science	Plant-based formulations showed promising UV absorbance and natural sun protection.

3. Aim and objective

Aim:

The purpose of this study is to prepare Sunscreen lotion using *Glycine max* Seeds Water Extract and Evaluate lotion

Objective:

- 1 To Formulate Sunscreen lotion using *Glycine max*.
- 2 To Evaluate Screen Lotion using various parameter.

4. Plan of work

1. Selection of plant-based information
2. Literature survey
3. Authentication of plant.
4. Extraction of *Glycine max* Seeds by Cold Maceration
5. Formulation of Sunscreen Lotion
6. Evaluation of Sunscreen Lotion

5.Experimental Work

5.1. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The plant had been collected from the surrounding area of S.M.B. T campus Dhamangaon Nashik,

Maharashtra and botanically identified and authenticated by Dr. Darshan. Kokate Head Dept. of KSKW ASC College voucher No SMBT/COG/GM/2024 25/32.

2. Drying and storage

Plant seeds properly in shade dried overnight at 38^oc and make a fine powder by grinding dried plant parts, make very fine powder and store in plastic polythene bag protecting from moisture, air, sunlight. This packed powder is use for the extraction and further experimental work.

Fig.4 Cold Maceration

Fig.5 Extract

3. Preparation of Extract

The plant's seeds were gathered, and they were carefully cleaned to get rid of any excess dirt. These were shade dried for 15 days under normal environmental conditions. They were powdered using a blender. 20g powdered crude drug was kept into beaker and add 200ml of distil water (1:10), Powder After being continuously extracted with water by Cold Maceration for 7 Days then filter and extract is collected, then concentrated using electronic water bath.

Phytochemical Tests for detection of flavonoid

The obtained extract underwent the preliminary phytochemical tests for determination of the phytoconstituents specifically flavonoids, phenols and terpenoids.

1. Test for Flavonoids

Flavonoids are known for their antioxidant and UV-absorbing properties, making them beneficial in sunscreen formulations.

A) Shinoda Test

- **Procedure:** A few pieces of magnesium ribbon were added to the ethanolic extract, followed by dropwise addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

- **Observation:** Development of a pink to scarlet coloration indicates the presence of flavonoids.

B) Lead Acetate Test

- **Procedure:** The extract was mixed with a few drops of 10% lead acetate solution.
- **Observation:** Formation of a yellow-colored precipitate confirms flavonoids.

C) Sulphuric Acid Test

- **Procedure:** A small amount of extract was treated with concentrated sulfuric acid.
- **Observation:** Appearance of a deep yellow solution indicates flavones/flavonols.

D) Zinc Hydrochloride Test

- **Procedure:** The extract was treated with zinc dust and hydrochloric acid.
- **Observation:** Development of a pink to red color confirms the presence of flavonoids.

2. Test for Phenolic Compounds

Phenolic compounds contribute to photoprotection and anti-inflammatory effects.

A) Ferric Chloride Test

- **Procedure:** The extract was treated with 5% ferric chloride solution.
- **Observation:** Formation of a deep blue or green color indicates phenolic compounds.

B) Lead Acetate Test

- **Procedure:** A few drops of lead acetate solution were added to the extract.
- **Observation:** A white or cream precipitate indicates the presence of phenolics.

3. Test for Terpenoids

Terpenoids have anti-inflammatory and skin-protective roles in topical formulations.

A) Salkowski Test

- **Procedure:** The extract was mixed with chloroform, followed by the addition of concentrated sulfuric acid.
- **Observation:** A reddish-brown coloration at the interface confirms the presence of terpenoids.

B) Liebermann–Burchard Test

- **Procedure:** The extract was treated with acetic anhydride followed by concentrated sulfuric acid.
- **Observation:** Formation of a blue-green ring indicates terpenoids.

4. Test for Saponins

Froth Test

- **Procedure:** The extract was diluted with water and shaken vigorously.
- **Observation:** A persistent froth lasting 10 minutes indicates saponins.

Table No 3 List of Ingredients for Formulation

Ingredients	Category	F1 (0.5%)	F2 (1%)	F3 (1.5%)
Glycine max extract	A P I	0.1	0.5	1.0
Steric Acid	Emulsifier & Thickener	0.5	0.5	0.5
Liquid Paraffin	Emollient	1.4	1.4	1.4
Cetyl Alcohol	Co Emulsifier	0.1	0.1	0.1
Glycerin	Humectant	1.0	1.0	1.0
Methyl Paraben	Preservative	0.01	0.01	0.01
Potassium Hydroxide	Neutralizer	0.2	0.2	0.2
Distilled Water	Aqueous base	16.79	15.79	14.79
Rose oil	Fragrance	2 drops	2 drops	...

Procedure for preparation of Lotion

The production of sunscreen formulation was divided into two parts: the oil phase (phase A) and the water phase (phase B).

Sunscreens were formulated using the combination of phase A and phase B through melting of ingredients at 65-70°C for 30 minutes.

The sunscreen lotion bases were then incorporated with accurate amounts of Glycine Max extract according to formulation in Table

The determination of its properties were made after the production of sunscreens

Fig no 7 Formulation batches F1, F2, F3

5.2 Evaluation of Sunscreen lotion

5.2.1 Organoleptic Properties: Physical appearance: Visual inspection was done on the color, homogeneity, consistency, and phase separation of the Sunscreen formulations made Glycine max extract.

5.2.2 pH measurement the pH of the lotion compositions was measured using a digital pH meter. pH measurement: The pH of the produced lotion compositions was determined using a digital pH meter. One gram of gel was dissolved in ten

milliliters of distilled water, and the mixture was then allowed to sit for two hours. The pH of each formulation was assessed three times, and average readings were calculated.

5.2.3 Uniformity Each created gel formulation's homogeneity was visually inspected after the gel was placed in a container. We looked at their appearance and aggregate content.

5.2.4 Extrubality The lotion compositions were put into standard capped collapsible aluminum tubes, and the ends were sealed with a crimp. The weight

of each tube was noted. The tubes were placed between two glass slides and clamped. The cap was removed once the slides had been covered with 500 g.

5.2.5 Spreadability It is determined in terms of how long it takes for two slides to separate from gel that is placed in their small gaps under the influence of a specific load. Spreadability is improved if two slides can be separated in less time.

Spreadability was determined by applying the accompanying formula:

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Were,

S = Spreadability,

M = Weight in the pan,

L = Length moved by the glass slide and

T = Time (in sec.) taken to separate the slide completely each other

5.2.6 Sun Protection Factor (SPF)

The SPF (Sun Protection Factor) is a measure of the sunscreen product's ability to protect the skin from UVB radiation. It was determined using spectrophotometric analysis within the wavelength range of 290–320 nm, which corresponds to the UVB region responsible for erythema (sunburn). A 200 mg sample of the formulated sunscreen was accurately weighed and transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask. Ethanol was added as a solvent, and the contents were vortexed thoroughly to ensure complete dispersion. Ethanol was used as a blank. The absorbance of the resulting solution was recorded using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer across

wavelengths 290 nm to 320 nm, at 5 nm intervals, using a 1 cm quartz cuvette.

The SPF value was calculated using the following equation:

$$SPF = CF \times \sum_{320}^{290} EE(\lambda) \times I(\lambda) \times Abs(\lambda)$$

Where:

- CF = Correction Factor (typically 10)
- EE(λ) = Erythemogenic effect at wavelength λ
- I(λ) = Intensity of solar light at wavelength λ
- Abs(λ) = Absorbance of the sample at wavelength λ

The values of (EE × I) are constants obtained from literature (e.g., Sayre et al., 1979), and the SPF is computed as the summation of the product of these constants with the measured absorbance at each corresponding wavelength.

6 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic Properties

Table no 4 Organoleptic Properties

Sr.	Batch	Colour	Odour
1.	F1	White	Characteristic
2.	F2	Off White	Characteristic
3.	F3	Light Cream	Characteristic

Organoleptic properties of all three batches were evaluated and the observation were recorded in table

Homogeneity

Table no 5 Homogeneity

Sr. No.	Batch	Homogeneity
1	F 1	Good
2	F 2	Good
3	F 3	Good

pH

Table no 6 pH

Sr No	Batch	pH
1	F 1	6.4
2	F 2	6.5
3	F 3	6.6

Fig no 8-pH measurement

All the batches were evaluated for pH using pH meter in triplicate method and means were recorded in table. All the batches were found to be in the desired pH range.

Spreadability

Table no 7 Spreadability

Sr No	Batch	Spreadability(gm.cm/sec)
1	F 1	30.46
2	F 2	26.66
3	F 3	24.42

Spreadability was evaluated using Spreadability apparatus and the values were recorded in table

Fig no 9 Spreadability

Extrubality

Table no 8 Extrudability

Sr No	Batch	Extrudability
1	F 1	Good
2	F 2	Good
3	F 3	Good

Sun Protection Factor (SPF)

Table no 9 Absorbance

Wavelength	EE(λ) x I (λ)	Measured Absorbance (Abs(λ))			EE x I x (Abs(λ))		
		F1	F2	F3	F1	F2	F3
290	0.0150	0.70	1.00	2.60	0.010	0.015	0.039
295	0.0817	0.95	1.10	2.55	0.077	0.089	0.208
300	0.2874	0.92	1.35	2.48	0.264	0.388	0.712
305	0.3278	0.88	1.25	2.30	0.288	0.409	0.753
310	0.1864	0.75	0.85	1.90	0.139	0.158	0.354
315	0.0839	0.60	0.45	1.20	0.050	0.037	0.100
320	0.0180	0.50	0.50	0.90	0.009	0.009	0.016
					$\Sigma 0.828$	$\Sigma 1.096$	$\Sigma 2.166$

Fig no 10 Double Beam UV Spectrophotometer

Fig no 11 Dilutions

Table no 10 SPF

Sr no	Batch	SPF (CF x Σ)
1	F 1	8.28
2	F 2	10.96
3	F 3	21.66

Fig no 12 Graph of absorbance

7 CONCLUSIONS

The present research work, “Formulation and Evaluation of a Water-Based Sunscreen Lotion Incorporating *Glycine Max* Extract,” aimed to develop a stable, effective, and cosmetically acceptable sunscreen formulation using a natural bioactive agent.

The prepared water-based lotion demonstrated promising sun-protective activity, as evidenced by its favorable SPF value and other evaluation parameters. The incorporation of *Glycine max* extract, known for its antioxidant and photoprotective properties, contributed to the formulation’s efficacy in shielding the skin from harmful UV radiation. The formulation

also exhibited good Spreadability, stability, and aesthetic appeal. These findings suggest that *Glycine max* extract serves as a potential natural alternative to synthetic UV filters in sunscreen formulations. Further clinical and in vivo studies are recommended to validate its long-term effectiveness and safety profile.

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